

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

November, 05-06 2022
Ethno Complex Vrđnickska kula, Vrđnik

European Curricula in Radiation Oncology, Clinical Oncology and Inter-Specialty Training

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Curricula are valuable as they inform both trainees and educators about the competences they need to acquire in order to become good oncologists. They empower the trainee to focus on what is important and educators to design learning experiences. They set expectations for what is acceptable in a training programme and a blueprint for the content and methods of assessment.

The European Core Curriculum for Radiation Oncology/Radiotherapy was revised in 2019 to produce a 4th edition. The aims of the ESTRO curriculum are to develop comparable standards for training across Europe and to facilitate free movement of specialists across borders. It is also hoped that it will improve the level of training across Europe and will make the non-medical expert roles more explicit. A clinical oncology module, developed in 2012 can be combined with the ESTRO core curriculum to enable clinical oncology trainees to follow a single curriculum.

A study on the implementation of the 4th edition of the ESTRO core curriculum showed that its content and values were endorsed across diverse geopolitical and sociocultural regions. Barriers to curricular implementation were identified, however, at the organisational and systems level and included insufficient teaching faculty, lack of coordination and the need for influential leadership.

In 2021 the European Commission launched a call for bids to develop an 'Inter-specialty cancer training programme.' Focusing on oncology, surgery, radiology and cancer nursing, the programme wishes to deliver a more skilled and mobile cancer workforce through cross-border training and information-sharing. The aim is to optimise collaboration among cancer specialists and ultimately benefit diagnosis, treatment and follow-up for cancer patients. The European Cancer Organisation coordinated a successful bid from 29 beneficiary organisations and 4

associated partners from 16 EU countries, to fund the Innovative Collaboration for Inter-Specialty Training Across Europe project (INTERACT-EUROPE). In the initial part of the project a needs assessment has included a scoping literature review looking at interprofessional training in oncology, with a survey and a qualitative study to address the question, "What is it valuable for trainees to learn in order to work more effectively with different specialties and professions to deliver better care and to provide psychosocial and nutritional support for cancer patients?" These have been used to develop 125 competences for the INTERACT-EUROPE curriculum organised according to the CanMEDS framework.

Keywords: curricula, radiation oncology, education, training

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